

Miscanthus as a Companion Crop for Enhanced Timber Production in Agroforestry Systems

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Testifield with Miscanthus and treerows, Praktijkpunt Landbouw Vlaams-Brabant

Miscanthus x giganteus, commonly known as elephant grass, is a perennial crop that can grow up to three meters tall and produces a fiber-rich biomass at harvest. This biomass has numerous applications across various sectors, ranging from bioenergy production to construction materials and animal bedding. Despite its promising bio-economic potential, miscanthus—similar to agroforestry—is still rarely cultivated in Flemish fields. The crop has a 20-year harvest cycle and can be harvested once a year. It requires minimal maintenance; weed control is only needed during planting and the early growth phase. Miscanthus is highly adaptive and can grow on a wide range of soil types, from sandy soils to heavy clay. An additional benefit is its phytoremediation capability, allowing it to restore and make productive use of contaminated or marginal soils. When combined with tree rows, for example, for the production of high-quality timber, miscanthus offers additional advantages. The competition between miscanthus and the trees encourages the trees to grow taller with fewer lower branches, improving timber quality. While trees are only harvested after 15 to 50 years, miscanthus provides an annual yield, enhancing the economic viability of such combinations. The versatility of miscanthus makes it a valuable addition to sustainable agricultural systems. The crop can support the production of bioenergy, animal bedding, fiberboards, and other construction materials. Moreover, it contributes significantly to carbon storage and soil quality. Because both miscanthus and trees remain in the field for extended periods, they enhance the quality of both the timber and the soil. Over a 20-year period, miscanthus can substantially improve degraded or marginal lands, contributing to a more sustainable agricultural landscape in Flanders.

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